

Therapeutic Community Model in Treating Substance Abusers

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Introduction

Drug abuse is not new but matter has been getting worse in recent months as a significant chunk of young generation is being lost to this menace that has literally shattered the physical and mental health of Punjab's youth.

Every aspect of the drug abuse has an element of money that is associated with it. In the absence of a strong policy and a scientific approach at the end of the government, 5000 plus de-addiction and rehabilitation center in Punjab, and 200 private centers in Delhi Government Hospitals are unable to alter the structure and dynamics of drug abuse.

Other than the efforts made by Alcohol Anonymous and Narcotic Anonymous who use 12-point programme along with Cognitive Behavioral Therapy and Rational Emotive Therapy, another model of treatment has proved to be more effective in the rehabilitation of addicts. Therapeutic Community (TC) models still in its experimental stage in India but it has been more successful in terms of its approach and outcome.

In the following paper an attempt is being made to scrutinize the issue along with some historical and cultural dimensions in a new perspective of Therapeutic community intervention. To begin with it would be important to explore the related terms in order to make a case of usage of therapeutic community model.

An addict is a normal human being. What differentiates him from others is the fact that he has chosen drugs as a means of attaining temporary happiness. These drugs have slowly but gradually overpowered his whole identity to an extent that they have become an end in themselves. Erstwhile productive member of the society has been debilitated to such an extent that he has completely lost his own self-esteem and his whole world has

been circumscribed by a dose of drugs. This process of degradation not only destroys his nervous system but his whole world too. All this society also ostracizes him and pushes him to a dead end.

Drug addiction is a disease like any other. But lack of awareness and society's antipathy to a drug addict aggravates the situation. Psycho-socio-traumatic experiences take away all the constructive reason for addict's existence.

Objective The study is aimed at understanding the concept and approach of Therapeutic Community model in treatment in cases of substance abuse and addiction. This also intends to describe detoxification and de-addiction of clients and to underline the professional limitation and delimitations in the model with respect to its use in community.

People will usually find it easier to deal with their problems if they are in a supportive environment. A therapeutic community programme aims to create the right conditions for people to change undesirable behaviors and learn new ways of doing things. It can be very useful for helping the individual deal with problems such as addiction. The focus is on the life of the individual and not just on their specific symptoms. This type of environment is artificially created, but the individual will be able to take what they learn and use this in the outside world.

The Therapeutic Community is designed to foster healthy lifestyles, abstinence from addictive substances, and the identification of other areas of needed change. The community itself functions as a teacher and guide to sustained recovery.

The Therapeutic Community represents a highly structured environment with defined moral and ethical boundaries. Participants in a TC setting are residents, as in any family setting, not patients in an institution. These residents play a significant role in managing the TC and acting as positive role models for others to emulate. There is a sharing of meaningful responsibilities, and the hope that residents will develop a true investment in the community. Residents and staff alike are facilitators, emphasizing personal responsibility for one's own life and for self-improvement.

In a Therapeutic Community, peer interaction and feedback is the catalyst that changes negative behavior into positive change and personal insight. It

is the TC, alongwith the individual that accomplishes the process of positive change in the resident. High expectations and high commitment from both residents and staff support this change. Insight into one's problems is gained through group and individual interaction. However, identifying feelings, conquering fears, learning through experience, and failing and succeeding and experiencing the consequences of success and failure are considered to be the most potent influence toward achieving lasting changes.

Four-sided approach of therapeutic community model and long-term treatment programme rejuvenates the primordial spirits of the addict and take him on a journey of regainment of health and total bliss. Drug addiction is not merely a chemical problem but a problem with deep roots connected to the addict's lifestyle and all the personal and social association that come with it. An addict is someone who believes in personal and instant gratification, having led a life of complete emptiness. He finds himself caught in the web of addiction and spends his days spinning lies to himself to justify his very existence. This is the universal truth of the addict.

"Drug addiction is a state of periodic and chronic intoxication detrimental to the individual and to society, produced by the repeated consumption of a drug (natural or synthetic). Its characteristics include: (1) An overpowering desire or need (compulsion) to continue taking the drug and to obtain it by any means; (2) A tendency to increase the dose; (3) A psychic (psychological) and sometimes a physical dependence on the effects of the drug." [Source: WHO Expert Committee on Drug Dependence. Sixteenth report. Geneva, 1969 (WHO Technical Report Series, No.407)]

The entire TC programme derives its tools and therapies, considering the operational definitions designed by health organizations. TC is broadly 12-18 months, multi-directional programmes specifically divided in four phases. These phase are further designed to the need specification based on the principles of case work and group work. The individual comes to the programme either as a substance user or as an addict, commonly termed as client by professionals.

"The primary goal of a Therapeutic Community is to foster individual change and positive growth. This is accomplished by changing an individual's lifestyle through a community of concerned people working together to help themselves and each other." - Therapeutic Communities of America, Inc.

Phase I

This is orientation phase. It is the period where the residents are given an opportunity to get acquainted with the program, its rules, philosophy, process and terminology

Phase II

This is primary treatment stage for the client when the client deals with withdrawals and psychological diffidence. The individual plans to reintegration into mainstream living, involving family, vocational educational and social aspect of life. In TC first the detoxification is done using clinical approach under the supervision of doctors and paramedical staff.

Phase III

In this phase, re-entry facilities are usually separate from primary treatment and are organized to accommodate resident's increased time in outside activity. During this phase, vocational, educational plans and goals are initiated. Finance, food and lifestyle changes usually create anxiety and there for the use of the groups becomes necessary for managing anxiety and stress. Relapse prevention work is increased significantly.

Phase IV

Generally termed as After Care, this is a complete separation from residential care. Planned group attendance and social support help to stabilize the individual's lifestyle. Most of the clients return to their life as usual.

Given this backdrop, it is rather easy to understand the need for TC as a treatment method for addiction. This Community treats addicts not as physical, emotional or moral cripples but as people who can reacquire the ability to live and enjoy normal lives. It believes that one is not supposed to be judged by his past alone but more for what he does honestly in the 'Here & Now' to correct his mistakes.

Community - Group of people

The community has the primary therapeutic vehicle to foster behavioral

and attitude change. Addiction is primarily a behavior other than a disease. This model serves as a learning laboratory in which clients learn and practice the skills and responsibilities that they will need to function adequately in their home community. Each member expected to be a contributing number of his society. The governing principles of Group work practice, often come in conflict with practical needs and challenges of community. Still the entire group is further divided to subgroups based on the respective therapeutic engagements.

Hierarchy, Discipline, Laws and Rules

The very primary approach of all the associated approaches is reintegrating the addicts in an artificial community. History of TC can be traced back to synanon community, Alcoholics Anonymous and Oxford Group movement.

History of Therapeutic Community

Synanon

All Therapeutic programmers are decedents of one programmer Synanon, is the first ever self-help, no doctors, drug rehabilitation programme, founded by Charles "Chuck" Dederich Sr. (1913–1997) in 1958 in Santa Monica, California. The name was chosen when a member slurred the words "Symposium" and "Seminar." One of its early cardinal rules was "no violence" or threat of same. It went from the first ever no doctor involved self-help drug rehab (Synanon I), to a building of a new society in Synanon cities to lead the world into the 21st Century (Synanon II), to becoming a self-claimed religion (Synanon III).

Short comings are to be shared in the community and the punishment (restitution) for shortcomings are also provided by community. That's why it's a correctional community, not only for alcoholics but other purpose also.

Oxford movement

Frank Buchman, a Lutheran minister, began a movement which he originally called "A First Century Christian Fellowship." In 1928 the name of the movement changed to the "Oxford Group." The thrust of the movement was experience rather than clear biblical doctrine. Frank founded it with an

aim of spiritual rebirth of humanity formed the Oxford group .Practices were public sharing, guidance, commitment to change and making restitution.

Alcoholics Anonymous

Alcoholics Anonymous is one of the most renowned organizations that exist to help individuals recover from alcoholism. Millions have benefited from the programmes and weekly meetings, and AA has influenced countless other programmes, treatment centers, and those that work with alcoholics. What may not be so well-known, however, is the history of AA and the events that have occurred to make the organization what it is today. Alcoholics Anonymous was created in 1935 by recovering alcoholic Bill Wilson. Wilson had been failing at his Wall Street career because his drinking was so out of hand that he was admitted into the hospital a number of times. Friends tried to help Bill, including his childhood drinking buddy, Ebby Thacher. Ebby had found sobriety through the Christian movement, called the Oxford Group, and he firmly believed it changed his life. Dr. William Duncan Silkworth of the Towns Hospital in New York City also influenced Bill Wilson with religion, saying that alcoholism is a disease and that only God can cure it. With a newfound relationship of his own with God, Wilson was able to finally quit drinking for good.

Day Top

Daytop started in 1963, under the leadership of Dr. Daniel Casriel along with Monsignor William B. O'Brien who is the president of Daytop.

"Back in the 1950s, it was the desperation of the addicts and their families that convinced me something must be done to give these people hope."

The diffusion of Therapeutic Community

Therapeutic Community as a model of treatment has proved its significance across the globe. Many countries have adopted it because of its triangulation of medicinal, psychosocial and community based approach.

This has a flexibility to adjust to different cultural and religious groups that makes it more acceptable across the board. TC has its diffusion in Europe, Asia, Middle East, Latin America, West Indies and Oceania.

Therapeutic Community Environment or Trans Disciplinary Staffing

A TC environment consists of Doctors, Counselors, Teachers, Psychologist, Nurse, Family Therapist, Social Workers and Maintenance Administrator. The staff in this treatment community consists Trained Para-leadership, Trained Para-professional (Recovery Staff), Academically Trained Professionals, Social Work trainees, Research Scholars, RN (Registered Nurses) Therapeutic Community.

Significance of Therapeutic Community

This system is just like any model of treatment programme with the above list of staff. The difference lies in the way they relate to the client, to each other and outside world. Besides the regular professional roles and responsibilities, the staff is expected to fully participate in community life.

Essential Elements of Therapeutic Community

There are nine essential elements of the TC model, often termed as the acting principles of TC. These elements are based on social learning theory that utilizes the community to foster behavior and attitude change. They are Active Participation, Membership Feedback, Role Modeling, Collective Formats for Guiding Individual Change, Shared Norms and Values, Structure and System, Open Communication (even the bathrooms are open), Individual and Group Relationship and Unique Terminology (detbally-those who have no feelings, Ghasri, Wind-up (TC)).

Hierarchical Social Structure

Therapeutic Community has hierarchical structure to support the community functioning. It is being followed in different treatment stages of the client. The air is to facilitate the addict to behave with different levels of responsibilities in the family. It is important to mention that this is an administrative setting and no individual at any stage is above confrontation. The structure is chronologically arranged as:

- Crew member
- Ramrod
- Expediter
- Department Head

- Shingle
- Coordinator of department
- Staff In-charge of department

Treatment Plan

As the focus of the TC model is on Behavior, feeling and thinking, during the entire 12-18 month long treatment, the individuals often shuffle back and forth in the hierarchy structure. The rewards and punishment based on individual's behavior and group participation, is a projections of clients progress In Therapeutic Community. Every stage and phase covers the biological, psychological, behavior correction and social learning of the individual client.

What Makes Therapeutic Community Work

Positive Reinforcement: "I am doing it", "so can you". "I will", "we will", help one to become the man or women, she/he are capable of being.

Self-Help: The model help the client to help programme. It provides individuals with the tools, needed to help him rebuild life. The operative words are one's life. The bottom line is: "What lengths are you willing to go, to change".

Tough Love: It will give to you what was given to it, "responsible love and concern". Community will not accept anything that conflicts with or contradicts our value system. TC will demand behavioral change. TC has three cardinal rules and they are No Physical Touch, No use of Alcohol or any other Drug and No Sexual Involvement with anyone on any level within the Family.

Family: It is a family that aspires to the highest ideals. From the moment client is accepted in interview, he becomes family. The model does understand the need of social networking and importance of different institutions with in the social structure, the family believes in self sustenance when it comes to finances. Being a family TC has a set of underlining therapeutic modalities, as followed:

- Structured and safe environment. The emphasis on family values and participation.

- The use of positive peer influence.
- To help overcome perceived helplessness, lack of self- efficacy, inadequacy, low self-esteem.
- Pro-social values through modeling by staff and peers.
- Strong sanction by the community against deviant behavior.
- Emphasis on achievement by increments or small steps- learning by doing & modeling.
- Emphasis on involvement or participation.
- Emphasis on the value of self-reliance or educational/ vocational training.
- Emphasis on cooperative efforts/mutual assistance.

Therapeutic Tools

The Therapeutic Community model of treatment of de-addiction and behavior correction is a action based programme. There are many tool used to execute values drawn from Daytop and Synanom philosophy.

Initial Interview

Addicts come to treatment for a variety of reasons and under different circumstances which determine their motivation for treatment. The benefits of undergoing TC programme are well explained to him. TC is closed community structure, surrounded by paper walls. Grounding is done to facilitate the acceptance, very first and the most important set in process of rehabilitation.

Open Door Facility

Although TC is a 12-18 month programme, recommend to family and client a closed setting, resident are open to enter the treatment and leave it at any time. In line with the philosophy, the structure does not practice with symbols of detentions and do not have door locks anywhere.

Five stages of changes

- A) Pre Contemplation – The client has no intension to change behavior in the foreseeable future. He is unaware or under aware of his problem. He is in denial of defensiveness.
- B) Contemplation – The member seriously think that the problem exists and have the intension of overcoming it. But he does not make any commitment to take any action for it. Not ready to act.
- C) Preparation – As an individual, person recognizes and admit to his problem. He is reevaluating his options among courses of action available. He is ready to make changes.
- D) Action - He modifies his behavior, experience or environment in order to overcome their problems. The action based approach needs considerable time and energy. He has made effort toward problem resolution.
- E) Maintenance- People work to prevent relapse and consolidate the gains attained during action stage. It is a continuation rather than absence of change.

The four Distinct but Overlapping Categories of Therapeutic Community Tools are Emotional Psychological, Behavior Shaping, Intellectual Shaping and Vocational Survival.

Hierarchy of Behavioral shaping tools

1. **Talking to** is a form of verbal correction regarding an observed behavior or attitude. It provides information in a positive way about how individual are expected to behave in the community. One to one correction of done by a group of senior members to young members
2. **Spoken to (ST)** is a serious reminder given by a senior member and peer to a young member conducted in a private and formal manner.
3. **Dealt with (DW)** In DW message is given by 2-3 senior member with direct focus on his behavior. The client is asked to stand straight, with eye contact, hands folded back and not to argue at all.

4. **Verbal Haircut** - When negative behaviors and attitudes become recurrent, the verbal haircut is used. It is highly structured verbal reprimand delivered by staff and peer. Its tone is more serious and there is maximum use of dissonance to induce change.)
5. **Learning Experience (LE)** - Often combined with a Haircut LE is a form of restitution for persistent non-compliance with community expectations
6. **Chair** - The chair reinforces the idea that certain behaviors are outside the expected norms of the community. this fixture is not used for any other purpose. The individual on the chair is outside the community and thus is ignored except staff. The chair is used to create a time for thinking and reevaluating.
7. **General Meeting** - It is called in response to a serious behavior infraction, often taboo behavior that endangers the entire community-" Violation of three Cardinal Rules: No Violence, No Sex, No Drug)
8. **Expulsion** – Expulsion is used as the last tool considering the collective welfare of the family. This is done in consultation with the significant others to the client.

Encounter Groups

Every member can put in slips against an individual focusing on a particular act or behavior. The family sits in a circle, where the session is facilitated by SOD and Staff in the family. Negative emotions towards peer are effectively expressed and managed in Encounter group.

Big Brother

A junior client (Little Brother) is allocated a senior member as a big brother to guide him in TC until the former is able to understand the concepts of TC.

Pull-Ups

Shot-comings, Carelessness, behavioral and attitudinal deformities are brought to notice of the House in the Morning meeting. This work as a tool to acceptance and breaking of denial.

Static Group

The entire family is substructure based on their psycho-social needs, members or clients under a counselor are called Static Group. They evaluate the overall performance of the individuals.

- More like classic group psychotherapy
- Members remain in group for an agreed upon time
- sharing of historical information but focus on "Here and Now"
- Focus on group relationship and pattern of behavior
- Frequency 1-2 times per week
- Ideal composition is 8-15 members

Conclusion

The TC is a style of treatment that engages the whole person in the recovery process and challenges the individual to have a full, positive life with healthy supportive relationships and satisfying work. TC is Self-help, social learning treatment model. It is a therapy that gives *relief, cure, and treatment method*.

The TC is a self-help programme whose primary goals are the cessation of substance abuse behaviors and fostering personal growth. Community activities lead members to learn about themselves in the areas of emotional, intellectual and spiritual condition, behavior management, and survival skills, which may include vocational and/or educational assessments.

TC also believes in the capacity of Man to change, and to better himself. It stands to dispel the myth "once an addict always an addict". It has disproved it by presenting those who have overcome addiction and are living productive lives. The addict here is given help to help himself, and treated as a person capable of "normal" things in life. He gets a very clear message that here at last is a place that is willing to give him a chance to earn a place under the sun.

The whole process of recovery from addiction, involves in large measure the ability of the addict to be able to step out of his limited space, share in the pain or failure of another and offer a helping hand. This in turn increases his commitment to his own recovery, for how can one enlighten another unless he believes in what he teaches. The TC is the anti-thesis of what the

former addict lived by. To be in recovery, it is essential for the addict to give up self-love and find solace in faith or belief in God or a higher power.

The TC also believes in the power of the Human Values. It uses a more practical term quality to describe values. In order for a recovering addict to realize his essential freedom, his personal dignity, and be able to take responsibility for self, his life and conduct should be of positive quality.

The TC believes that people can change and that learning occurs through challenge and action, understanding and sharing common human experiences. Considering addicts as a progressive disease the model focuses on the cause more than the symptoms. The methodology of the TC is participatory in nature hence the outcome is likely to be a lasting one.

The model still has to work on the relapse rate which is very high. Though the duration of the programme is exponentially long as compared to other models, it does not guarantee permanent sobriety.

References

Davinder Mohan & Anita Chopra, (2003) , Alcohol Consumption In India, , Report by AIIMS

M. Martin ,(2011),Adolescents Alcohol Consumption, , Master Thesis at Erasmus University Rotterdam

George De Leon, (2009) The Therapeutic Community : Theory, Model, and Method, Spring Publishing Company.

Fernando B. Perfas, (2009) The Therapeutic Community : Social System prospective, Universe Company.

Davendra Agochiya, 2009,Every Trainers Handbook, SAGE Publication India.
http://www.who.int/substance_abuse/terminology/who_lexicon/en/(accessed on 28/06/2013)

<http://treatmentTherapeuticCommunityommunitiesofamerica.org/> (accessed on 28/06/2013)